

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 1

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 2

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 3

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 4

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 5

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 6

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 7

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 8

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 9

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 10

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 11

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 13

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 14

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 16

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 17

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 20

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 21

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 22

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 24

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 25

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 27

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 29

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 31

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 34

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 39

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 40

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 41

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 42

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 43

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 44

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 46

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 47

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 48

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 49

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 50

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 57

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 60

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 61

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 64

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 65

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 67

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 70

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 71

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 72

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 73

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 74

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 75

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 79

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 80

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 84

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 87

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 88

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 90

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 91

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 93

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 94

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular

ID: 95

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: theoretical-modular
ID: 99

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

